

The Transcreation of a Novellete to Film

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Abstract:

*A novel that is chosen for adaptation poses various levels of challenges to the script writer and the film maker. What are those challenges and how do the writer and film maker address them? The texts that I have chosen to study here are the novelette **Manju (Mist)** and its film adaptation. The film was not much appreciated by the audience as was expected since the novellette was a much loved one. What could have been the reason for this failure?*

Keywords: Films, adaptation, female protagonist.

M. T. Vasudevan Nair's novelette **Manju (Mist)** was much loved by the public. So when the film was announced the anticipation was also sky high. But the film didn't create any impact on its viewers. It was impossible to figure out what could have gone wrong with a film that was based on one of the most beautiful stories penned by M.T. Vasudevan Nair. In the foreword to **Manju (Mist)** (1964) K P Sankaran opines that this novelette by MT Vasudevan Nair is by all means close to music in its sheer poetic passages and fluid movements as well as its resounding still moments. One couldn't agree more with this statement. It is so easy to fall in love with this little story about a school teacher (a Malayalee) in Nainital. The entire novelette is written in such elegant language about one of the most picturesque landscapes in the world. The sheer beauty of the land stands in stark contrast to the monotonous existence of the unmarried school teacher who lives away from her family in Kerala.

The story centers on Vimala, a high school teacher, who lives a lonely life. Her family consists of an adulterous mother who cheats on her bed ridden father, a brother who is a drug addict

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and a sister whose main plan in life is to trap a man into marriage. She lives away from this group of neurotics in her school hostel where she is the warden as well. The novelette begins at the beginning of a vacation in the school. A vacation means plenty of lonely times for Vimala, for she rarely visits her depressing family. In her loneliness she thinks of her past.

Her past holds the single vignette that she cherishes for life. A love affair marked a glorious vacation nine years back. The hero of that love affair is Sudhir Kumar Mishra one of the many tourists that frequent the valley of Nainital. He was the type that most young women would love the company of. He was well educated, having completed his research on certain facets of Indian society and was on a vacation to relax. Their chance encounter in the streets of Nainital leads to a romantic affair in which Vimala loses herself. At the end of the vacation Sudhir leaves promising to come back which he never does. Vimala gets trapped in the memories of Sudhir and refuses to try and move out of it. The novelette is a poetic narration of this painful waiting coupled with other tragic elements such as a dysfunctional family and their excessive behaviour.

Vimala's endless wait for Sudhir is echoed in Budhu, a boatman's endless wait for his 'gora' father who impregnated his mother during one of his vacations 17 years back. Thus in the bustle of this quaint tourist valley of Nainital the story of the quiet existence of two souls waiting is unraveled. Vimala is a peculiar character, in fact so peculiar that one may find such a person only in novels. She is so far from reality that the director found no difficulty in transcreating her for the film viewers.

The character is a stereotype. She is the quintessential passive old maid. There are no elements of iconoclasm in Vimala, neither in the novelette nor in the film. When the film was slated to be released there was much anticipation among the audience as the novelette was much loved by the readers. Since the film was directed by the writer himself there was much more expectations from the film. However, the film didn't live up to the expectations of the audience who, disappointed with the film, quickly left the theatres leaving the producers in tears. The film is now occasionally shown on Television in the afternoons. The slow moving pace of the film seemed to fit into the frame of lazy afternoons.

The problem with the film lies in the fact that the script never utilized the lavish time that was at hand since the source text was a novelette. The script writer, Shankar Mohan, who also essayed the role of Sudhir Kumar Mishra in the film reproduced the entire novelette and tried to stretch it to a two and a half hour length film. This left the film with plenty of freeze frame like moments. “The attempt to transplant the novel verbatim led Manju to its failure” (Eravankara 108). Added to this was the dream like quality of the source text which was full of personal musings and meditations. The author and the director failed to fill in these moments with some sort of action. The film maker made an adaptation that bore complete fidelity to the source text. He had reproduced the stereotyped Vimala of the novel just as the stereotyped Vimala in the film without effecting any changes.

Neither are the male characters of the novel changed. This is a rare situation. But the film failed to make an impact. Madhu Eravankara calls it one of the major disappointments of the eighties (Eravankara, *Malayala Cinemayum Sahityavum (Malayalam Film and Literature)* 78). In the list of different types of adaptations made from fiction to film, Eravankara gives a special slot to films based on short stories. Though Manju isn't a short story, it is a novelette and the variables of adaptation of short stories can be applied here as well. One of the major elements of adaptation of short stories is to interpolate the existing text to create new sub plots and characters to stretch the narrative to fill two or three hours of film viewing. Nothing of the sort was done in Manju. The level of fidelity is quite high in this case.

This proves that certain types of fiction require the film maker to intervene to create new levels of meanings for the film to make an impact on its audience.

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